

2020-2022 TRAINING REPORT

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The Netherlands eScience Center has been systematically collecting data on organized workshops since 2020. The aim is to document the development of the workshops and gather feedback from participants through pre- and post-workshop surveys. A total number of 735 respondents provided feedback through the pre-workshop survey, while 642 respondents completed the post-workshop survey. This feedback is analyzed to gain insights into participant perceptions and experiences.

This report provides insights based on the data collected on workshops organized by the Netherlands eScience Center in the years of 2020, 2021 and 2022.

NUMBER OF WORKSHOPS

The Netherlands eScience Center has hosted a total of 51 workshops in the years of 2020, 2021 and 2022. Most workshops in this period were delivered online due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

TOTAL OF

51 WORKSHOPS

1188 ATTENDEES

82 %

Online workshops

7

Externally funded workshops

23

Average attendees per workshop

71.4%

Attendance per workshop

WORKSHOP CONTENTS

Netherlands eScience Center has organized workshops on a wide range of topics.

17
DIFFERENT
TOPICS

*) 'Data Carpentry' includes four types of workshops, and 'Other' includes three different types.

40

In-house developed
workshops

11

Data and Software
Carpentry workshops

ATTENDEES BACKGROUND

The Netherlands eScience Center organized workshops for participants with different backgrounds

The main domains are Life Sciences & Health (LSH), Natural Sciences and Engineering (NES), Environmental Sciences and Sustainability (ENV) and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH).

DOMAINS OF WORKSHOP ATTENDEES (%)

OCCUPATION OF WORKSHOP ATTENDEES (%)

42 %

PhD Candidates

23.1 %

Research Staff

16.1 %

Postdoctoral Researchers

WORKSHOP EVALUATIONS

635 participants evaluated the workshop in the post-workshop survey. The graph shows the distribution of answers in percentages.

Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly agree

"I'm happy with the overall quality of the workshop"

"I would recommend this workshop to others who want to learn about the topic"

"The workshop was useful for my research or day to day work"

"The workshop improved my skills on the topic"

"This workshop will contribute to doing my work more efficiently"

"I have learned new things applicable to my work"

POSITIVE FEEDBACK FROM THE ATTENDEES

USEFUL WORKSHOP CONTENT

"All of the topics were really useful and interesting and I think all of them will be useful for me in near future"

COLLABORATION

"Coding together with little exercises in between was very useful and I enjoyed it a lot."

"Having the collaborative document to keep the participants engaged. "

HANDS-ON ATTITUDE

'I liked that the workshop was more hands-on as opposed to just listening to someone give a talk'
'The exercises are definitely the nicest and most educational to do'

INSTRUCTORS

'The group of teachers modeled a constructive, supportive working dialogue. The way they talked out loud through solving some problems or looking up some new information, and how they helped each other'

ATMOSPHERE

'Well organised to keep everyone engaged and promote critical thinking. Overall very satisfied from the experience!'

2020-2022

SUMMARY

51

Workshops hosted

40

Workshops developed by eScience Center

11

Data and Software Carpentry workshops

17

Different workshop topics

82 %

Online workshops

7

Externally funded workshops

1188

Attendees in total

23

Average attendees per workshop

Participant feedback

92 %

are happy with the quality of the workshop

89 %

agreed the workshop improved their skills

90 %

would recommend the workshop to others